

A Mutant Concept Drone for Underwater Surveys, Inspection, and Intervention

1st Benedetto Allotta
Dept. of Industrial Eng.
University of Florence
Florence, Italy
benedetto.allotta@unifi.it

2nd Jonathan Gelli
Dept. of Industrial Eng.
University of Florence
Florence, Italy
jonathan.gelli@unifi.it

3rd Marco Pagliai
Dept. of Industrial Eng.
University of Florence
Florence, Italy
m.pagliai@unifi.it

4rd Alessandro Ridolfi
Dept. of Industrial Eng.
University of Florence
Florence, Italy
a.ridolfi@unifi.it

Abstract—Unmanned vehicles, either in the aerial domain or in the underwater one share a critical aspect represented by the different requirements for a vehicle devoted to perform surveys on large areas and a vehicle devoted to close inspection and intervention on structures.

On the one hand, for an Unmanned Underwater Vehicle (UUV) devoted to close inspection and intervention (either Autonomous - AUV or Remotely Operated - ROV) the desired shape is a compact, “stocky,” ROV-like one, with actuators placed so as to obtain an isotropic thrust/mobility behaviour and to ensure a) hovering with good position/orientation accuracy and b) mobility in any “direction” rejecting disturbances related to current and vertical motion of the water due to waves if the vehicle is near the surface. On the other hand, for the design of an AUV devoted to perform survey on large areas of seabed (such as to perform inspection on a pipeline), the preferred shape is torpedo-like and accurate hovering capability is not a requirement: That is why commercially available AUVs usually have a single aft propeller and control surfaces to control pitch and yaw thus preventing the possibility to perform hovering.

In the present paper, a novel mutant underwater concept drone is presented, featuring reconfigurable shape and actuator distribution which adapt to the task at hand. By doing so, we suggest how to avoid “mission impossible” attempts of achieving a good trade-off between the torpedo-shaped, hydrodynamic design, preferred for surveys, and the stocky, isotropic design, preferred for hovering tasks.

Index Terms—UUV, AUV, ROV, Survey, Inspection, Intervention, Maintenance, Marine Robotics

I. INTRODUCTION

In the aerial domain as well in the underwater one, unmanned vehicles are more and more used to perform surveys on large areas of land or seabed or to perform close inspection of infrastructures and plants by means of various sensor payloads. The intervention capabilities by means of robot arms mounted on unmanned vehicles is currently reserved to tethered, remotely operated underwater vehicles (ROVs) [7], used mainly in the Oil&Gas industry. Only some very recent results exist of research on autonomous underwater manipulation [4] [14].

This work has been supported by Project SUONO - Safe Underwater Operations in Oceans, funded by the Italian Ministry of Education, University, and Research in the framework of the competitive call on Smart Cities and Communities - Topic on Marine technologies (2014 - 2019).

In the following we will use “hovering” tasks to refer to close inspection and intervention tasks and “survey” tasks to describe survey tasks of large areas.

For Unmanned Underwater Vehicles (UUVs) devoted to hovering tasks, the desired shape is a compact, “stocky,” ROV-like one with actuators placed so as to obtain an isotropic behaviour and to ensure a) hovering with good position/orientation accuracy and b) mobility in any “direction” rejecting disturbances related to current and vertical motion of the water due to waves if the vehicle is near the surface. Suitable metrics to evaluate UUV thrust/mobility isotropy might be derived from the manipulability ellipsoids first proposed in [13]. On the other hand, for the design of an AUV devoted to survey tasks on large areas of seabed (such as to perform inspection on a pipeline), the preferred shape is torpedo-like and accurate hovering capability is not a requirement: That is why commercially available AUVs usually have a single aft propeller and control surfaces to control pitch and yaw rates, thus preventing the possibility to perform hovering [12]. Even torpedo-shaped AUVs featuring hovering capability thanks to the adoption of additional vertical and horizontal thrusters perform poorly when asked to sail sideways [3].

At the same manner, in the aerial domain, multirotor drones are used for hovering tasks whether fixed wing drones are preferred for their energy efficiency when surveys task are to be performed. Recently, fixed-wing, vertical take off drones have become commercially available, following the concept of Vertical Take-Off and Landing - VTOL aircrafts (tiltrotor or vectored thrust) that have been proposed in the XX century.

In the underwater domain, some attempts have been made to design compact vehicles with better hydrodynamics and actuator layout so as to be able to perform “survey tasks” as well as “hovering tasks.”

Two of the authors of this paper have addressed the issue of optimal thrusters layout in an underwater vehicle with given shape [2].

The design of a new compact vehicle with redundant actuation named Zeno AUV has been presented in [5]. The first prototype has been tested in archaeological campaigns in the Mediterranean Sea in collaboration with the Israel Antiquities Authority. Thanks to a 8-actuator configuration, Zeno AUV features full hovering capability (with 6 actively controlled

DOFs) and isotropic behaviour, so as to effectively counteract lateral current, ideal for close inspection. In addition Zeno AUV shape is quite hydrodynamic in order to be able to perform surveys on relatively large areas.

However the requirements for vehicles intended to perform “survey tasks” or “hovering tasks” are so different that the level of optimality of the mentioned trade-off designs based on improved actuator layout and improved hydrodynamic shape is quite low.

In the present paper, a novel mutant underwater drone concept is presented [1], [10], featuring reconfigurable shape and actuator distribution which adapt to the task at hand. By doing so, we suggest how to avoid “mission impossible” attempts of achieving a good trade-off between the torpedo-shaped, hydrodynamic design, preferred for survey tasks, and the stocky, isotropic design, preferred for hovering tasks.

II. CONTEMPORARY RESEARCH

A review of current research on underwater vehicles is presented in [11]. Only very few attempts to design new vehicles which can adapt their configuration to the task at hand can be cited.

[6] propose a humanoid robot aimed at diving on archaeological sites. The humanoid robot concept is intrinsically reconfigurable and may adapt to the task at hand. However the humanoid design approach is probably not the best to address the design of a reliable, persistent underwater vehicle devoted either to perform IRM tasks on submerged structures and subsea factories or surveys on large tracks of seabed.

[8] propose a snake robot which can be seen as a “two arm” vehicle which is intrinsically reconfigurable and may, in principle, use the multi-thruster configuration and the snake self-motions to compensate for external disturbances during free-floating manipulation tasks. Complementary, the slender shape of the snake allows to efficiently perform survey tasks when all the snake links are aligned along the surge direction. However the expected level of thrust/mobility isotropy and omnidirectional shape stability which is possible to achieve by changing the snake configuration is not high.

[9] propose a vehicle which changes its shape transforming itself from a compact hydrodynamic shaped AUV to an intervention UUV with two arms which unfold to perform intervention tasks. The vehicle changes a little bit its shape in order to achieve better fluid static stability and thrust/mobility isotropy but such a change is not drastic as in the here proposed design.

III. THE NEW DESIGN

We propose a novel concept of multiclass reconfigurable vehicle capable to synthesize a Survey AUV, an Inspection UUV and an Intervention UUV in a single machine. The design allows the vehicle to “mute” between a slender, “survey” configuration and a stocky, “hovering” configuration and a patent application on this idea has been filed [1]. The vehicle will potentially have the ability to autonomously switch between the two main configurations and/or choosing an intermediate

one, according to the task at hand and the environmental conditions. The vehicle shall use the survey configuration to dive with the best fluid dynamic efficiency for long distance runs with minimum power consumption. Conversely, it shall use the hovering configuration when it reaches a point of interest where close inspection and/or intervention tasks are to be performed even in free-floating mode [4] [14] and in the presence of external disturbances. Switching from the survey configuration to the hovering configuration does not only drastically change the fluid dynamics and fluid statics of the vehicle but it also changes the actuator pattern, so as to improve thrust isotropy.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Allotta, J. Gelli, M. Pagliai, A. Ridolfi, “Veicolo sottomarino a configurazione variabile,” Italian patent application 10201800007463, 2018.
- [2] B. Allotta, M. Pagliai, L. Pugi, “Redundant and reconfigurable propulsion systems to improve motion capability of underwater vehicles,” *Ocean Engineering* 148, 2018, pp. 376-385. doi:10.1016/j.oceaneng.2017.11.03
- [3] A. Caffaz, A. Caiti, G. Casalino, A. Turetta, “The hybrid glider/auv folaga,” *IEEE Robotics Automation Magazine* 17, 2010, pp. 31-44. doi:10.1109/MRA.2010.935791
- [4] G. Casalino, G. Torelli, A. Sperindè, A. Turetta, “Floating Underwater Manipulation: Developed Control Methodology and Experimental Validation within the TRIDENT Project,” *Journal of Field Robotics* 31, 2014, pp. 364-385. doi:https://doi.org/10.1002/rob.21497
- [5] J. Gelli, A. Meschini, N. Monni, M. Pagliai, A. Ridolfi, L. Marini, B. Allotta, “Development and design of a compact autonomous underwater vehicle: Zeno auv,” *IFAC-PapersOnLine* 51, 2018, pp. 20-25. doi:10.1016/j.ifacol.2018.09.463
- [6] O. Khatib, X. Yeh, G. Brantner, B. Soe, B. Kim, S. Ganguly, H. Stuart, S. Wang, M. Cutkosky, A. Edsinger, P. Mullins, M. Barham, C. R. Woolstra, K. N. Salama, M. L’Hour, V. Creuze, “Ocean one: A robotic avatar for oceanic discovery,” *IEEE Robotics Automation Magazine* 23, 2016, pp. 20-29. doi:10.1109/MRA.2016.2613281
- [7] D.M. Lane, J.B.C. Davies, G. Robinson, D.J. O’Brien, M. Pickett, D. Jones, “Amadeus: advanced manipulator for deep underwater sampling,” *In Proceedings of International Conference on Robotics and Automation*. vol. 3, 1997, pp. 2145–2151. doi:10.1109/ROBOT.1997.619280
- [8] P. Liljebäck, R. Mills, “Eelume: A flexible and subsea resident imr vehicle,” *In OCEANS 2017 - Aberdeen*. 1-4. doi:10.1109/OCEANSE.2017.8084826
- [9] J.E. Manley, S. Halpin, N. Radford, M. Ondler, “Aquanaut: A new tool for subsea inspection and intervention,” *In OCEANS 2018 MTS/IEEE Charleston*. 1-4. doi:10.1109/OCEANS.2018.8604508
- [10] M. Pagliai, A. Ridolfi, J. Gelli, A. Meschini, B. Allotta, “Design of a reconfigurable autonomous underwater vehicle for offshore platform monitoring and intervention,” *In 2018 IEEE/OES Autonomous Underwater Vehicle Workshop (AUV)*. 1-6. doi:10.1109/AUV.2018.8729776
- [11] Y.R. Petillot, G. Antonelli, G. Casalino, F. Ferreira, “Underwater robots: From remotely operated vehicles to intervention-autonomous underwater vehicles,” *IEEE Robotics Automation Magazine* 26, 2019, pp. 94-101. doi:10.1109/MRA.2019.2908063
- [12] P. Stevenson, M. Furlong, D. Dormer, “Auv shapes - combining the practical and hydrodynamic considerations,” *In OCEANS 2007 - Europe*. 1-6. doi:10.1109/OCEANSE.2007.4302483
- [13] T. Yoshikawa, “Dynamic manipulability of robot manipulators,” *In Proceedings. 1985 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*. vol. 2, 1985, pp. 1033-1038. doi:10.1109/ROBOT.1985.1087277
- [14] D. Youakim, P. Ridao, N. Palomeras, F. Spadafora, D. Ribas, M. Muzzupappa, “Moveit!: Autonomous underwater free-floating manipulation,” *IEEE Robotics Automation Magazine* 24, 2017, pp. 41-51. doi:10.1109/MRA.2016.2636369